

Water and nutrient retention using bio-inspired drainage filters in the agriculture landscape, Austria

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Introduction

This work is part of WATERAGRI, an H2020 research and innovation project aiming to re-introduce and enhance water retention and nutrient cycling solutions to enable sustainable agriculture and cope with climate change challenges.

Preserving water resources in view of population increase and climate change is a significant environmental challenge (UN, 2016). Management of water resources can reduce pollution, supporting sustainable agricultural food production and ecosystems in line with the bio-economy concept (EC, 2012). Wateragri addresses the topic of integrated water management in small agricultural catchments. The project aims to re-introduce nature-based solutions, such as constructed wetlands and bio-inspired drainage systems in the agricultural landscape, leading to better water retention and nutrient retention. Through this pilot, we implemented a bio-inspired multi-layer drainage system in farmland.

Agricultural run-off has high spatiotemporal flow variability (winter/summer) and low nitrogen and phosphorus concentration. alchemia-nova, in collaboration with BOKU, has developed a multi-layer vertical filter system to address such agricultural runoff on the slope of an agricultural field in Mistelbach, Austria. The goal was to construct a pilot bio-inspired multi-layer filter system and study its ability to retain nutrients present in agricultural runoff.

Methodology

Three vertical-flow multi-layer systems operating in parallel were constructed above ground in three IBC tanks (1.2 m²) in June 2021, on agricultural land in Mistelbach. They received surface runoff from a 30 m² cropped land with 1% soil inclination (Figure 1). The three filter systems were installed in parallel and filled with different substrates to mimic a vertical-flow filter system. They were designed according to the Austrian guideline for vertical flow wetlands ÖNORM 2505. The filters differed in terms of substrate used in the main-layer and presence of vegetation: biochar/unvegetated, draingarden/vegetated, soil, and vegetated, respectively. The filter systems received surface runoff through a three-way distributor, every time there was enough precipitation to produce surface runoff. The agricultural surface runoff of a 10x3m confined area was collected with a pipe 30 m long, so the water flows per gravity on top of the filter systems.

The runoff infiltrated vertically through the system (vertical flow), and outflow is measured with a tipping counter, connected to a PLC datalogger and PV panel. Therefore, this experimental prototype system was composed of three parts: a) the catchment area, including piping, b) the filter array with water distribution, c) the PV island with monitoring and sensors.

Figure 1. Top-view and side view of the experimental site in Mistelbach, agricultural runoff is collected and distributed by gravity in parallel on top of three filter systems.

The bio-inspired filter systems consisted of vegetated or not vegetated filter systems, composed of biochar, Draingarden™ and zeolite, or just soil as a reference filter material as the primary filter. Figure 2 and Table 1 shows the characteristics of each filter.

Figure 2. Bio-inspired multi-layer filter composition.

Table 1. Multi-layer composition of the three drainage filter systems.

Layer composition	Filter 1	Filter 2	Filter 3
Vegetation	No	Yes	Yes
Top layer (12 cm)	Gravel 8-16 mm	Draingarden	-
Main layer (30 cm)	MgOH coated biochar	Draingarden* + 10% zeolite	Soil (Sandy/Loam)
Bottom layer (24 cm)	Gravel 8-16 mm	Gravel 4-8 mm, 8-16 mm	Gravel 4-8 mm, 8-16 mm

(*) **Draingarden*** fine no compost + 10% vol coarse zeolite

Different parameters were monitored in the effluent of the three filter systems: ammonia, nitrate, orthophosphate, pH, EC, while temperature and soil moisture sensors were installed in two depths of the filter system (17 and 30 cm). Tracer experiments using 50 L of 25 mS/cm NaCl were also carried out to have insight on filter hydraulic efficiency.

Potential Expected outcome

The primary expected outcome is to test the capabilities of the bio-inspired filter to work as a water retainer and a nutrient retainer addressing agricultural surface run-off. The filter system, if upscaled, can be of practical use for the farmers to keep the surrounding waters cleaned; in cases of excess nutrient concentrations present in agricultural runoff, such filter system may serve as a water and nutrient retainer. This approach may result in economic value by re-using the saturated biochar as fertilizer and improving the soil structure, thus increasing soil fertility. The system is expected to be low maintenance, from harvesting the plants yearly and changing the biochar when it is saturated with nutrients.

Conclusions

The proposed system has the potential that, if upscaled, may provide water retention capacity and nutrient recovery potential. The recovered nutrients (phosphorus, and nitrogen) can then be recycled using the saturated biochar filter as fertilizer. Moreover, the system benefits from being a climate change adaptation approach in capturing agricultural surface runoff.

References

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